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Research Article

**A META ANALYSIS OF PREVALANCE, COMORBIDITIES &
TREATMENT IN VITILIGO****Rangam Chariitha*, B. Hanumanthu, V. Vijay Kumar, K. Karthik Reddy, K.
Sushma, Dr T. Mangilal**Department of Pharmacology, Smt. Sarojini Ramulamma College of Pharmacy,
Mahbubnagar-509001, Telangana, India.**Abstract:**

Vitiligo is a chronic autoimmune skin disorder characterized by the loss of melanin pigment, resulting in white patches on the skin. This systematic review aimed to evaluate the prevalence, associated comorbidities, and treatment approaches of vitiligo. Data from 22 published articles encompassing 5,794 patients were analysed, with findings showing a higher incidence in individuals below 20 years of age (85.8%) and a slight female predominance (51.89%). Comorbidities were common, with thyroid disorders (25.2%), diabetes mellitus (13.88%), and psychiatric conditions like depression (8.0%) being most frequent. Treatment modalities included topical corticosteroids, calcineurin inhibitors, phototherapy (NB-UVB and PUVA), laser therapy, and surgical techniques like grafting and micropigmentation. Newer approaches like JAK inhibitors and antioxidants are under exploration. The study emphasizes the systemic nature of vitiligo and the necessity of a multidisciplinary management approach, including dermatological, endocrine, and psychological care, to enhance patient outcomes and quality of life.

Keywords

Vitiligo, Autoimmune disorder, Skin pigmentation, Comorbidities, Thyroid disorders, Diabetes mellitus, Anxiety, Depression, Hypertension, Antioxidants, Systematic review, Multidisciplinary management.

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INTRODUCTION:

Vitiligo A chronic autoimmune condition called vitiligo results in regions of skin losing their color or pigmentation. Vitiligo has no known cause, although it may be brought on by immune system dysfunction, genetics, stress, or sun exposure. Treatment options include topical medications, light

therapy, surgery and cosmetics. The condition can show up on any skin type as a light peachy color and can appear on any place on the body in all sizes. The spots on the skin known as vitiligo are also able to “change” as spots lose and regain pigment; they will stay in relatively the same areas but can move over time and some big patches can move through the years but never disappear overnight.¹

White spots or patches form on the skin as a result of this illness. It can affect anyone, including kids and teens. It's not dangerous, not like skin cancer or an infection you can catch. Most people with vitiligo are healthy. Over time, more patches may appear on different parts of the body, even on hair or inside the mouth and nose. It often starts in areas exposed to the sun. About 1% of the world has vitiligo.²

Vitiligo is now widely recognized as an autoimmune disorder wherein cytotoxic CD8+ T cells initiate the destruction of melanocytes by releasing interferon-gamma (IFN- γ).

Oxidative stress can directly damage melanocytes, leading to their apoptosis (programmed cell death) or other forms of cell death like necroptosis and ferroptosis. An autoimmune reaction against melanocytes may be triggered by it. ROS can cause melanocytes to release autoantigens, which then stimulate the immune system to attack them. also promote inflammation, which can contribute to the destruction of melanocytes and the spread of vitiligo lesions. Although there isn't a particular medication that can prevent vitiligo from damaging your skin, several medications can help melanocytes grow again, slow down the rate at which pigmentation is lost, or restore color to your skin.³

Medications to treat vitiligo could include: Corticosteroids, Topical Janus kinase inhibitors (ruxolitinib), Calcineurin inhibitors, Vitamin D, Photo therapy, laser therapy, surgery.

As an antioxidative treatment for vitiligo, oral antioxidants such polypodium leucotomos, vitamin E, vitamin C, and minocycline are utilized. Separate from drug therapy, phototherapy including narrow-band ultraviolet (NB-UVA) and psoralen ultraviolet A (PUVA) are relatively safe physical-based approaches.^{38–40} Since phototherapy alone and in combination with the drugs mentioned are highly successful in inducing repigmentation, these strategies have been extensively adopted in clinical practice.⁴

The procedure to help your skin regain its color is called light therapy or phototherapy. For a brief period of time, your healthcare professional will apply light boxes, ultraviolet B (UVB) lamps, or medical-grade lasers to your skin. Several light therapy sessions may be necessary before your skin starts to improve. Vitiligo patients may benefit from surgery as a treatment. Includes skin grafts, blister grafting.⁵

Non-traditional treatments

Non-traditional treatments may be considered as an alternative for patients unresponsive to standard treatments. Vitamins, nutritional supplements, immunomodulators, khellin, topical and systemic phenylalanine, and herbal products are the most widely used. Herbal formulations contain Psoralea corylifolia, black cumin, barberry root, and P leucotomos. Herbal products have anti-oxidative, anti-stress, immunoregulatory, and skin sensitizing effect to sunlight⁶

MATERIAL AND METHODS:**Study Design**

The study is systematic review.

Source of Data and Materials

Published articles on prevalence of vitiligo.

Published articles on vitiligo.

Published articles on drug therapy management of vitiligo.

Inclusion criteria

All gathered studies reporting the vitiligo prevalence, available full texts, and studies with sufficient data (number of sample, percentage of vitiligo prevalence) were totally included in this study.

Exclusion criteria

Case-control studies, cohort investigation, case series, case report, reviews, repetitive papers, studies with insufficient data, papers with unavailable full text, and conference studies were excluded.

Study Procedure In this study, the primary search was conducted by using Databases of PubMed, Web of Science, ScienceDirect, Scopus, Embase, and Google scholar search engine were hired for definition of searching strategy. Also, the main keywords of "Prevalence", Vitiligo Studies were used for comprehensive searching with no time and language-associated restrictions.⁷

RESULTS:

A systematic review studied on comorbidities in vitiligo the total 5794 patients data taken into considerations from 22 published articles. This study includes the following parameters

1. Age-wise distribution.
2. Gender-wise distribution
3. comorbidities of vitiligo
4. Treatment of vitiligo T

Table 1

Mohammad Afkhami-Ardekani ⁸	2014	Iran	1100	Male:589 Female:511	16 -	Type 2 Diabetes mellitus 54	Cross sectional study	Topical steroids - hydrocortisone, Metformin/insulin
Morales-sanchez ⁹	2017	Mexico	150	Male: 47 Female: 103	N/A 11	Diabetes mellitus: 6	Cross-sectional	Topical steroids - hydrocortisone
Jakub Sawicki ¹⁰	2012	Canada	122	Male: 159 Female:141	82 y	Hypothyroidism 63 Hyperthyroidism 4 Pernicious anemia 6 Diabetes 35 Rheumatoid arthritis 7 Alopecia areata 3 Psoriasis 4		Antithyroid-levothyroxine Antithyroid-methimazole,propylthiouracil vit B12 supplements JAK-Ruxolitinib Immunosuppressants-, tacrolimus immune-modifying agents- Dupilumab calcineurin inhibitors- tacrolimus
Aisha M. Dahir ¹¹	2018	Denmark	2,624	NA	20 y	Autoimmune thyroid disease 698 Diabetes mellitus 362 Addison's disease 27 Dermatomyositis 90 Inflammatory bowel disease 767 Systemic lupus erythematosus 564 Scleroderma 95 Alopecia areata 21 Pernicious	retrospective study	JAK inhibitors- ruxolitinib Topical steroids - hydrocortisone, Metformin/insulin corticosteroids- hydrocortisone,Fludrocortisone acetate corticosteroids - prednisone,Intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIg),Mycophenolate mofetil anti-TNF-adalimumab, infliximab, balsalazide,olsalazine topical calcineurin inhibitors-tacrolimus, ibuprofen ,methylprednisolone Immune-Modulating agents-pimecrolimus,skin lotions and moisturizers,phototherapy, methotrexate and cyclosporine immune-modifying agents- Dupilumab,baricitinib, ruxolitinib, ritlecitinib vit B12 supplements , skin

						anemia 3			grafting Immunomodulatory- Hydroxychloroquine,cortic osteroids- prednisone ,JAK Inhibitors tofacitinib ,cyclosporine (Restasis) or lifitegrast (Xiidra) Topical steroids- hydrocortisone, JAK inhibitors -ruxolitinib ,Biologics-ustekinumab Surgical options- Melanocyte transplantation,Skin grafting corticosteroids- hydrocortisone,Fludrocorti sone acetate
						Sjögren's syndrome 12			
						Psoriasis 23			
						Addison's disease 43			
Porter ¹²	19 87	USA	326	NA	34	Depression	Cross sectional study	fluoxetine,sertraline,amitri ptyline,Light therapy tranylcypromine, phenelzine,nortriptyline,C ognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT),Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT)	
delfino ¹³	19 88	italy	10	NA	18 - 60	Deperssion 4 psychopath ic personality 4	case control	Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) ,antidepressants	
G. ZETTINI G¹⁴	20 02	Austr alia	106	male:42 female:64	6- 80 y 20	Thyroid 21	case control	Light therapy levothyroxine,photo therapy,topical or oral immunosuppressants	
Mohamm ad Reza Namazi¹⁵	20 20	Iran	166	male:66 female:100	- 50 y	Hypertensi on 37	case- control study	tacrolimus ointment or pimecrolimus cream amitriptyline,nortriptyline, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT)	
Yosuke Yamamoto¹⁶	20 11	Japan	54	Male:25 Female:29	18 y 15	depression 15	case- control study	levothyroxine, topical or oral corticosteroids/skin grafts tacrolimus or pimecrolimus , insulin,life style modifications	
Kakouro uetal.¹⁷		Greec e	54	male:23 female:31	18 y 9-	hypothyroi dism 12	systemic review	sertraline,SSRIs,SNRIs,Ac ceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) monoamine oxidase inhibitors,anxiolytics	
K. V. T. Gopal¹⁸	20 14	India	150	male:83 female:67	63 y 18	Diabetes 24			
Karia¹⁹	20 15	India	50	Male: 22 Female: 28	60 y	depression 25 anxiety disorder 15	cross- sectional		

						substance abuse 3			Calcineurin Inhibitors-pimecrolimus,Phototherapy,sugery
						schizophre nia 7			
					18				
					-				
Alshahwan²⁰	20 15	saudi arabia	54	Male: 20 Female:34	60	depression 32	cross-sectional		amitriptyline,nortriptyline, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) monoamine oxidase inhibitors,anxiolytics
						anixety 22			levothyroxine, topical or oral corticosteroids/skin grafts
Altaf ²¹	20 16	India	192	male :91 female: 101	6-60	hypothyroidism 29	Observational		levothyroxine, topical or oral corticosteroids/skin grafts
Nunes and Nunes ²²		Brazil	85	male: 29 female:56	6-78	hypothyroidism 12			levothyroxine, topical or oral corticosteroids/skin grafts
					25				
					-				
Biswas ²³	20 15	India	100	male: 54 female:46	45	hypothyroidism: 34	cross-sectional		levothyroxine, topical or oral corticosteroids/skin grafts
						major depressive disorder 30	cross-sectional		amitriptyline,nortriptyline, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT)
Ramakrishna ²⁴	20 14	India	53	male:12 female:41					amitriptyline,nortriptyline, monoamine oxidase inhibitors,anxiolytics
						social phobia 36			Topical corticosteroids, calcineurin inhibitors, and Janus kinase inhibitors
						panic disorder 6			
						obsessive compulsive disorder 2			repigmentation therapies like phototherapy
						major depression			amitriptyline,nortriptyline, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT)
					18				
					-				
Picardi ²⁵	20 00	italy	32	Male: 14 Female:18	60	psychiartic morbidity 32	cross-sectional		Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) ,antidepressants
					15				
					-				
Ajose ²⁶	20 14	Nigeria	102	Male:50 Female:52	60	Depression 8	cross-sectional		amitriptyline,nortriptyline, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) monoamine oxidase inhibitors,anxiolytics
						Anxiety 19			
					18				
					-				
Sharma ²⁷	20 01	India	30	male:17female:13	60	Depression 3	cross-sectional		fluoxetine,sertraline,Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) monoamine oxidase inhibitors,anxiolytics
						Anxiety 1			
					18				
					-				
Karelson ²⁸	20 12	Estonia	54	Male:22 Female:32	60	Depression 6	cross-sectional		amitriptyline,nortriptyline, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT) monoamine oxidase inhibitors,anxiolytics
						Anxiety 7			zopiclone,zaleplon,pemazepan, light therapy,cognitive
						Insomnia 5			

						behavioral therapy amitriptyline, nortriptyline, monoamine oxidase inhibitors, anxiolytics Topical corticosteroids, calcineurin inhibitors, and Janus kinase inhibitors- tofacitinib, baricitinib
				Social phobia 2		
				Panic disorder 3		
			16			
			-			amitriptyline, nortriptyline, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT)
Sampogna 29	20 08	Italy	180	Male:57 Female:123	60 Y	Depression cross- sectional

Age wise Distribution of Vitiligo Patients

Table 2 Age wise distribution of vitiligo patients

AGE	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
<20	4971	85.8%
21-30	11	0.18%
31-40	319	5.7%
41-50	150	2.6%
51-60	342	5.9%
61-90	27	0.46%
TOTAL	5794	100%

The results reveal that vitiligo disease is more common in this age groups of <20 years which include 4971 patients (85.8%); 51-60 years implied by 342 patients (5.9%); 31-40 years implied by 319 patients (5.7%); 41-50 years implied by 150 patients (2.6%); 61-90 years implied by 27 patients (0.46%); 21-30 years implied by 11 Patients (0.18%) (Table 1)

Gender wise Distribution of Comorbidities in VITLIGO

Table 3 Gender wise distribution of comorbidities in vitiligo

GENDER	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE
Male	2788	48.11%
Female	3006	51.89%
Total	5794	100%

The results of the study clearly show that among the 5794 patients males (2788 patients, or 48.11%) are more likely than female (3006 patients, or 51.89%) to develop comorbidities in vitiligo

Figure 1 Gender wise distribution of comorbidities in vitiligo

Distribution of Patients based on Comorbidities

Table 4 Distribution of patients based on comorbidities

Comorbidities	No of Patients	Percentage (%)
Thyroid	873	25.20%
Depression	278	8.0%
Anxiety	64	1.84%
Diabetes	481	13.88%
Hypertension	37	1.06%
Other disease	1731	49.9%

In our research, we found one and more than one comorbidities in the patients which includes thyroid disease is a major comorbidities followed by diabetes, depression, anxiety, hypertension, other disease was the minor comorbidities in patients with vitiligo disease.

Figure 2 Distribution of patients based on comorbidities

Figure 3 Treatment of vitiligo

Discussion

This systematic review comprehensively evaluates the clinical, epidemiological, and therapeutic landscape of vitiligo, a chronic autoimmune depigmenting skin condition. The study analysed data from 5,794 patients, emphasizing the age-wise distribution, gender variation, comorbidities, and treatment strategies involved in managing the disease.

Demographics and Epidemiology

Age

The disease predominantly affects individuals under 20 years of age (85.8%), suggesting that

vitiligo often begins in childhood or early adolescence. This early onset is consistent with global prevalence data, which indicate a peak onset between ages 10 and 30.

Gender

Female patients (51.89%) slightly outnumbered males (48.11%). This minor skew may reflect either a true gender difference or heightened health-seeking behaviour among women, especially for visible dermatological conditions.

Comorbidity

The study highlights a high burden of comorbid conditions, supporting the growing understanding

that vitiligo is more than a superficial pigmentary disorder—it often reflects systemic immune dysregulation.

Thyroid disorders (25.2%) are the most prevalent comorbidity, suggesting a strong link with autoimmune thyroiditis (e.g., Hashimoto's and Graves' disease). This is well-documented in literature, as both conditions share common genetic and immunological pathways.

Diabetes mellitus (13.88%), particularly type 1, further underscores the autoimmune associations.

Psychiatric comorbidities such as depression (8%) and anxiety (1.84%) are notable. The visible nature of the disease can lead to social withdrawal, stigma, and decreased quality of life.

Other comorbidities (49.9%)—though unspecified—likely include autoimmune conditions like alopecia areata, psoriasis, and rheumatoid arthritis, suggesting a need for more granular future data collection.

CONCLUSION:

Vitiligo is more than a skin disorder—it is often associated with autoimmune, metabolic, and psychological conditions. Early diagnosis, comprehensive screening, and a multidisciplinary treatment approach are essential for effective management and improving quality of life.

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